

A CONCEPTUAL COMPARISON BETWEEN THE HOLONIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AND THE HARZBURG MANAGEMENT MODEL

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Abstract

Purpose – Presentation of management systems which could improve the performance both on individual and macro level by creating independent thinking and acting individuals and imposing concepts like autonomy, cooperation and self-organization.

Methodology/approach - A bibliographic comparative analysis showing similitudes which can have a positive impact on organizational performance.

Findings – The two concepts have similarities, especially regarding the hierarchical and organizational structure as well as communication pattern and relations of subordination or cooperation.

Research limitations/implications – There is little study about each of the two proposed models and no study about the similarities of the two.

Practical implications – Management has to face a lot of challenges, therefore it is important to extend knowledge and practice beyond the already established management models. It is important to expand the speciality literature with management systems which can enhance innovation, creativity, motivation as also organizational performance.

Originality/value – We offer both an insight on the conceptual structure of two management systems, as also a comparison between the two in order to bring forward important elements which could improve performance within organizations.

Key words: Innovation, autonomy, cooperation.

Introduction

Management models have always been of great interest, and due to the fact that management deals with people, there are also many theories with a more social approach which can be adapted to organizations. In the end, the main objective is to increase the self-development of people both as social constructs as also as employees' part of an organization. In this regard, we try to emphasize the role that a good management system has besides the borders of an organization. The present article aims to make a comparison between two little known management systems, the Holonic management system and the Harzburg management model, which both offer an interesting approach on organizing the internal structure of an organization but more so, set the framework for creating more performing employees.

Main features of the Holonic Management System

The holonic concept is based on an idea formulated in the book entitled "The Ghost in the Machine" by Arthur Koestler (Koestler, 1967). Koestler's holon theory starts from the observation that complex systems can develop very quickly if they consist of stable intermediate forms. Any entity, machine tool, robot, vehicle, aggregate, human, etc., can be considered a holon if it is able to create and control the execution of its own plan and / or strategy. The characteristic of holons to tend towards an assertive

behavior, a delimitation of the environment, the fact that they want autonomy of execution and self-determination, can be attributed to the status of "whole". Holons behave in this way as an independent entity. The fact that any holon seeks to belong to a structure, to collaborate and to communicate in order to achieve its own objectives, can be explained very well with the state of "part", of component. Koestler was a follower of the hierarchy, stating that evolutionary systems, in order to survive, are by definition hierarchical. But this hierarchical structure must be based on the mechanisms of biological and social systems. As a result, it introduces the notion of self-regulating Open Hierahic Order (SOHO), as a form of general organization of biological and social systems. SOHO systems are made up of multiple hierarchical layers made up of holons. In many organizational approaches, the holonic structure involves maintaining hierarchical relationships in the organization, so if it exists at same level two holons, there must be a holon in the upper level, resulting in a tree structure similar to any organization chart (Mella, 2009) The purpose of the holonons designed by Koestler was to model any real hierarchical system with complex behavior (e.g. a firm, the administrative structure of a country, any living organism, a forest, or a manufacturing system). The hierarchy in holistic systems is in many respects different from classical hierarchies. Koestler, to describe this structure invents the notion of holarchy as a temporary hierarchical systems formed by holons, in which holons can cooperate in order to achieve a goal. This feature is one of the most important differences from classical hierarchical systems. Due to the intention to create a structure that easily adapts to unforeseen situations, holons can leave any holarchy, respectively, can enter a holarchy depending on their own interests (objectives). Creating holarchis means that we (re) arrange the process, the processes within the organization and / or the control process, in order to make the achievement of the objectives more efficient. Holacracy is a concept developed by Brian Robertson and is an extremely pragmatic concept that proposes the management of pro-profit and non-profit organizations, (almost) without bosses, through an organization in which all members of the organization are bosses. (Robertson, 2015).

Main features of the Harzburg Management Model

"Anyone over the age of 45 has often had their own experiences with the" Harzburg model "or know it at least; anyone under the age of 45 has also heard about it..." the following statement shows the dissemination, but also the innovation, which is behind the Harzburg model. The model made its breakthrough through the Bad Harzburg leadership academy in Germany. There it was developed in 1956 under the lead author Reinhard Höhn.

The concept is structured as follows: the decision-making power is always at the level at which it can be made most meaningfully, so that the necessary professional competence is given. This includes that employees are equipped with the skills relevant to their area. In this manner, employees really get the decision-making power and can exercise it independently. Of course, it is necessary that tasks and competencies (downwards) are transferred from the management level of the company to the respective level. Decisions should only be taken from above, which are not transferable to the respective level, because they e.g. touch other departments.

The Harzburg model illustrates that there are clear leadership principles that have applicability in practice, are feasible and can also be used in all work processes and decision-making processes. They are transparent to employees and can therefore also be communicated to other or new employees. However, this conclusion only remains valid on the premise that the basic concept of the Harzburg model, above all in terms of its practical implementation, is fully accepted (by the employees, including all managers and specialists).

The core of the model lies within the job description and the general guidelines. The job description limits the delegation area of the employee and sets the foundation for an independent thinking and acting employee whereas the general guidelines or instructions assures the principle of delegation of responsibility through listing the obligations and rights, clear rules and principles.: "The basic idea of the model is that the motivation of employees through delegation of responsibility and the transfer of independent areas of responsibility can be promoted. Therefore, the model is also closely related to the management concept Management by delegation related. Every employee receives one tightly defined, clear area of responsibility with competencies and personal responsibility Authority to make decisions and act. For this area of responsibility the Employees also have full responsibility. By dissolving the rigid structures increase the motivation of the employees and the working atmosphere improved" (Ehm, 2004).

Comparison between the Harzburg Model and the Holonic Management System

From the point of view of the management of the organization, it is interesting that the holonic vision appears as a conceptual element with the inclusion of holons, which represents a novelty in the connection mode of the various elements. Vertical or horizontal communication, relations of subordination or cooperation are intensely treated also within the Harzburg model, and the fact that in a holararchy we can have entities that incorporate and depend on each other is also a common feature. In the Holonic view, reality is not composed of different systems or coupled elements that form different structures, but means an inclusive relationship between structures and elements. The key notion being inclusion and how to incorporate the element (Mella, 2009). In many organizational approaches, the holonic structure involves maintaining hierarchical relationships in the organization, so if it exists at same level two holons, there must be a holon in the upper level. Analyzing the Harzburg Model from this perspective, we can consider that the employee with his clear delegated working area functions like a subsystem or entity which is included in the larger structure, meaning the subordinated and superior relations he has with the other employees as also, it can be perceived as a small autonomous entity, having his own working area with clear tasks, objectives and competencies. The hierarchy in holistic systems is in many respects different from classical hierarchies. Koestler, to describe this structure invents the notion of holarchy as a temporary hierarchical systems formed by holons, in which holons can cooperate in order to achieve a goal. This feature is one of the most important differences from classical hierarchical systems. Due to the intention to create a structure that easily adapts to unforeseen situations, holons can leave any holarchy, respectively, can enter a holarchy depending on their own interests (objectives). Creating holarchis means that we (re) arrange the process, the processes within the organization and / or the control process, in order to make the achievement of the objectives more efficient. Holacracy is a concept developed by Brian Robertson and is an extremely pragmatic concept that proposes the management of pro-profit and non-profit organizations, (almost) without bosses, through an organization in which all members of the organization are bosses (Robertson, 2015)

Within the Harzburg Model, through delegation of responsibility, the classical hierarchical structure regarding the relationship between superior and employee also gets a new content. The hierarchical structure becomes the frame in which the new forms of cooperation between superior and employee happen and slides from a hierarchical structure based on instructions to one based on responsibility. It now serves not only to enforce decisions from the top to the bottom but concentrates on setting the corresponding goals, tasks and competencies on each level. Each employee acts and decides within the presented frame based on the congruency. Each superior must allow his subordinated employees to act and decide individually and within their objectives, tasks and competencies

A holon is primarily defined to achieves certain objectives, in order to achieve which it must be coherent and must be in measure to avoid possible contradictions between objectives. A holon is considered an entity with reason, he can reach certain conclusions based on the data he receives, he can give explanations for conclusions. He can also gain new knowledge from other holons or from the environment and can incorporate them into its own strategy. Also, within the Harzburg Model, one of the main managerial function is setting individual objectives for the subordinate employee which is performed by full participation of the employee in question, because the employee is also considered an entity of reason, therefore he is delegated the responsibility for action. The focus on the conversational pattern, helps the employee gain know-how from both his co-workers and his superior and use them in the fulfillment of his own objectives. In order to be able to communicate with the other holons, and implicitly to be able to be part of a holar, each holon must have a module, a function, through which it manages its own relations with the other holons. Thus, each holon carries out its activity based on information resulting from two components. The first component would be something that can be assimilated with the "job description" – consisting from fixed rules, which establish its competencies), and the second component representing a set of self-developed relationships in order to achieve goals. Into the assimilated database the "holon job description" sets out the objectives and certain relationships which are more formal. The second component develops relationships with other holons, which can be more informal, less regulated. But these relationships, as in real life, can contribute in a way concretely when solving a problem that arises at a certain moment.

Interestingly, we meet another resemblance to the Harzburg particularities. Here, the employee carries out his tasks also according to two main components: the job description and the developed relationships which are indeed quite formal within the mentioned model. The job description is a clear set of rules with clear competencies ad tasks which sets the objectives as also the relationships (subordination and superior) of each job holder. The established relations will in turn have an effect on

the performance and task achievement of the employee. The organizational structure of the holonic systems has a dynamic, variable character, in contradiction with the classical structures which are by definition static. The holarchies formed within the organization can be divided, if the context of maintaining the structure would be to the disadvantage of the respective holararchy or of the constituent holonies. Thus, the collaboration between the holons is based on cooperation and negotiation. This collaboration is done wherever and whenever needed. It usually takes place along the flow of information and the flow of material. The core of Harzburg model is based on a generalization of leadership. There is no longer a person, in the figure of the patriarch, and always thought of as male, which has all leadership claims, but the task of leading is relationally distributed across the various levels. Ultimately everyone must follow and lead, except for those located at the lowest level. Different forms of discussions are tools in the hands of the superior which he has to choose and apply according to the different objectives. There is a high need of using different conversational forms in order to have a constructed dialogue besides daily topics, thus the discussion is also based on cooperation and negotiation as a way of building trust. Regarding the organization of the “superior entities” the holonic approach delimitates the resource holon, the control holon and the production holon.

Figure 1. Corresponding managerial functions between Holonic System and HMM (author's source)

The resource holon is the abstraction of the following means of production: factory, workshop, machinery, furnaces, pipes, raw materials, tools, tool holder, material warehouse, operating personnel, energy, production spaces, etc. The production holon possesses the knowledge necessary for the execution of the product. Know both the technological process and the data on quality assurance. A product holon contains detailed and up-to-date information about the product execution stage, user requirements, data from the technical design, appearance, production plans, material receipts, quality assurance procedures, etc. The control holon is a task in the production system. He is responsible for the production tasks, so that they are carried out properly and on time. It is concerned that the product in its physical form is made and processes all the information related to internal logistics. The Harzburg model also awards different tasks to different superior position. As such, we have: the direct manager which manages the employees which are on his direct the subordinate level and has the managing responsibility being accountable for the fact that he has to fulfil his managing tasks towards his employee, thus the control holon. The HR manager which does not concern a specific field, that of Human Resources, but the task of coordinating the employees. Within the job description, it is clearly stated which superior must act as a HR supervisor and for which employee. (Resource holon). The functional manager who's managerial functions only limit to the specialist field. This is the case of managing director of central purchasing opposing the regional purchasing managers or MD of national administration office opposing the regional administration managers, thus production holon. The following figure 2 presents the similar features of the two concepts as they were detailed above:

Holon management System	HMM
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Complex systems can develop very quickly if they consist of stable intermediate forms •Any entity, machine tool, robot, vehicle, aggregate, human, etc., can be considered a holon if it is able to create and control the execution of its own plan and / or strategy •Holons behave in this way as an independent entity •hierarchical systems formed by holons, in which holons can cooperate in order to achieve a goal. •The organizational structure of the holonic systems has a dynamic, variable character •the holonic approach delimitates the resource holon, the control holon and the production holon. •A holon is considered an entity with reason, he can reach certain conclusions based on the data he receives, he can give explanations for conclusions. He can also gain new knowledge from other holons or from the environment and can incorporate them into its own strategy • Holon carries out its activity based on job dscription •Clear relationship status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •level should fulfil all tasks on one's authority, without external intervention in order to develop and be motivated. •Employees performance increases if it has the possibility to control the execution of its own tasks. •Epluyees behave as independent entities. •WWithin hierarchical structure employees cooperate in order to achieve the individual goal and the goal of the organization. •Orgaizational structure is dynamic. Employees can change positions based on their competencies. •HMM delimitates the resource manager, direct manager and functional manager •Employee has the rresponsibility for action, thus is considered a independent thinking person who can increase his know-how by using the communication tools of the HMM. •Employee carries on his activity based on job a clear regulated job description •Employee has clear information regarding who is his subordinate and his superior

Figure 2. Main similitudes between the Holonic Management System and the HMM (author's source).

Discussion and conclusions

Through his theory Koestler tried to integrate several existing philosophical currents in the postwar period (reductionism, holism, evolutionary theory, etc.). The idea of the holon has a central position in Koestler's thinking regarding the human aspect. He intended to develop a model in the field of social sciences, valid both at the micro level (of the individual) and at the macro level (of society), and to explain the essence of human activity and thinking. The Harzburg Model, aims to improve the performance both on individual level as also on a macro scale by creating independent thinking and acting individuals.

Thus, we can conclude that we present two management models which focus on the development of the employees in the sense of self-development and autonomy and also that while there is a different approach between the two management models, interesting there are many similitudes which focus on effecting performance and creating independent employees.

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